

An integrated modelling framework for drone-based flood monitoring

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Abstract—The consequences of natural catastrophes, such as floods, can be devastating. To mitigate their impact, it is critical to carry out a rapid analysis of the affected region in the moments after they occur, in order to enhance situational awareness. For this purpose, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) may be considered as the technological basis onto which intelligent systems capable of providing support to rescue teams are built. In this work, we present a novel design of a single-agent architecture that can monitor environments affected by a flood event, and provide support to first responders in the decision-making process. In this framework, the autonomous UAV agent is capable of selecting regions based on a hydrological models and generate trajectories for monitoring and coverage. While monitoring the selected areas, the agent collects real-time data regarding water depth and water velocity. Exploiting the data collection process, the agent updates the selected regions, hence constantly updating its path. To demonstrate the proposed framework, we present a simulation study of a flash-flood which could affect the city of Nicosia.

Index Terms—Trajectory Planning, Model-predictive Control, Flood Monitoring

I. INTRODUCTION

In the past years, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), also referred to as *drones*, have been proven to be moderately effective in numerous applications such as smart agriculture [1], surveillance and monitoring [2], survey and mapping [3] and search and rescue (SAR) [4]. The effectiveness of UAVS in different applications motivated first responders to incorporate drones in disaster management. For example, a UAV could be used during a flood event to provide valuable aerial information to First Responders (FRs), enhancing the situation awareness and reducing the time for evaluating the risks, rescue endangered people or help them operate in a safer way.

Flash floods are considered as one of the major threats leading to loss of life, infrastructure damage, as well as enormous economic losses [1, 2]. Climate crisis, unsustainable natural resource exploitation, forest fires and unsuitable land use have altered the hydrological response of catchments. These factors increase the frequency and magnitude of floods [5].

For instance, Germany was one of the countries that suffered the most in 2021 due to pluvial floods ¹. The flash flood

that occurred the aforementioned year, claimed numerous lives. Additionally, vital services were damaged, such as the complete collapse of the network and infrastructure. Moreover, in a flash flood occurred in China in 2021 added to the overall death toll of 2021 ². Unfortunately, many regions do not have efficient prediction and mitigation strategies for flood events. Moreover, some regions may not have the experience to prepare people and FRs to initiate evacuation actions on time. The inadequate capacity of public authorities and rescue services to act diligently in these situations, increases the risks after the event [3, 4, 5].

An important factor for FRs in a flood event is the real time quantitative information. In most of the cases, there is little-to-no quantitative or real-time flood data available in urban environments during a flood event. UAVs could assist in mitigating this challenge, as mobile agents with real-time sensors.

Motivated by the challenges described above, this work proposes a system that could be deployed by FRs in order to increase their situation awareness during a flash-flood event. The proposed solution considers [6]: a) the low-level mission constraints such as the UAV dynamics (we model the UAV agent as a point mass with 3D linear dynamics) and sensing model (i.e., the geometry of the sensor’s field-of-view and sensing constraints). b) the mission objectives (i.e., the mission execution time and the UAV energy efficiency) c) the monitor of potential hazardous areas.

In this work we propose a framework dedicated to monitor specific areas of interest which can be used in order to automate the UAV-based monitoring of a flooded area. In particular, the proposed framework is unique in the sense that it considers UAV characteristics, mission-specific objectives, and mission constraints and produces UAV controls that enable the agent to autonomously navigate and monitor specific areas to achieve the mission objectives. The proposed framework integrates the UAV dynamic model, the UAV sensing model, and mission specific objectives into the search planning problem, hence eventually computing the UAV control inputs which generate successful search trajectories.

Overall, the contributions of this work are as follows: we

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¹<https://www.dw.com/en/death-toll-rises-above-100-in-german-floods-as-it-happened/a-58284256>

²<https://www.forbes.com/sites/isabeltogoh/2021/07/21/at-least-12-people-killed-in-chinas-henan-province-in-worst-flooding-in-1000-years/?sh=25de122135e0>

propose a novel monitoring framework which can be used to automate the UAV-aided missions in flooded or pre-flooded environments. We use the Digital Elevations Map (DEM) of the area and predict the floodplain (Fig. 1) at various times using an open-source flood prediction software (LISFLOOD). The integration of this prediction technique into the framework enables the drone to autonomously select cells of interest (higher momentum areas) and to generate a trajectory dynamically, by adjusting the waypoints based on data collection. The area is divided into grid-cells which allow the use of mathematical programming techniques, in order to formulate the search planning problem in 3D, using mixed integer linear programming (MILP) and solve it exactly using off-the-shelf optimization solvers. The end goal, is to provide valuable information in real-time to the FRs.

Fig. 1: 3D representation of the Nicosia Digital Elevation Map.

To briefly elaborate, in this work we introduce a controllable UAV agent that operates inside a confined 3D environment. The UAV agent advances in the 3D space according to its dynamic model and can monitor the surrounding area and collect water depth data according to its sensing model. The framework contains a grid map and each cell is a potential waypoint. The goal of the UAV agent is to search all waypoint cells in a predefined range of time. Simultaneously the UAV agent must optimize the mission objectives i.e., energy efficiency and mission execution time.

This paper is organized as follows: in Section 2 the overview of the Flood simulations techniques are described. Section 3 formulates the mathematical problem and provides an overview of the proposed framework. Section 4 develops the system model and Section 5 discusses the details of the proposed approach. Finally, Section 6 evaluates the proposed framework in a simulation study and Section 7 concludes the paper and discusses future work.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Flood Modelling

Flooding is a natural phenomenon that causes fatalities and property damage on numerous inhabited areas. It is among the most destructive, and frequent natural disaster affecting human societies. Flooding events occurrence and intensity may lead to fatalities and serious problems in necessary infrastructure.

Considering the impact flooding events have in urban and sparsely populated areas there has been a constant effort to comprehend, assess and forecast flood events and their impact. Flood inundation models are consequently developed to serve this purpose. Continuous efforts within the research community have considerably improved the capability of flood inundation modelling [7] [8].

A “brute force” solution to address this problem would be to model both floodplain and channel flows as fully three-dimensional and turbulent through the solution of the full Navier–Stokes equations. However, for typical flood wave flows (i.e. unsteady, non-uniform flows of high Reynolds number in a complex geometry) the direct numerical simulation of the Navier–Stokes equations is computationally prohibitive [7].

Typically, the purpose of any modelling application requires contextual attention to the output variables of predictive interest and their time and space scales, the level of accuracy required, and computational efficiency demands. The end users need to carefully select a model balancing their demands against model complexity and data requirements.

Two groups of approaches have gained the most attention and are the subject of continuing research: empirical methods such as measurements, surveys, remote sensing and statistical models evolved from these data-based methods [9]; and hydrodynamic models [7][9]. Recently though a third group of approaches had attracted some interest for modelling large flood plains and data sparse regions; these models can be categorized as simplified conceptual models and are based on more modest representations of physical processes, and have significantly shorter run-times than hydrodynamic models [7][9].

Regardless the active research in the field, rapid and accurate flood modelling at high spatio-temporal resolutions is still a significant challenge in hydrologic and hydraulic studies [10]. This is due to the complex nature of flooding and the multiple uncertainties currently enduring in flood inundation modelling [10]. Many new concepts, techniques and philosophical debates have detailed the difficulties of providing effective guidance and an agreement on the most efficient procedure [10].

The major sources of uncertainty in flood inundation modelling are [11]:

- errors in the model input data (principally hydrometric or rainfall-runoff model data to set boundary and initial conditions, topography data, friction parameters and details of any hydraulic structures present along the reach).
- errors in the independent observed data used to estimate model parameters or simulation likelihoods.
- model structural errors.
- conceptual model uncertainty as different classes of model may fit sparse validation data equally well, yet

give substantially different results in prediction.

The empirical methods for flooding events are based on observations of flooding events and data that were gathered through time. These data, including on-ground measurements, surveys, interviews, aerial photographs and satellite images, are actually a partial representation of the reality. They are obtained with underlying assumptions and unavoidable uncertainties, and hence should be treated as model results [7]. This type of modelling is considered robust and accurate. The results of these models are broadly used to support decision making and have aided as inputs to other types of methods; for example, remotely sensed flood extent has been widely used in flood monitoring, as well as a benchmark for hydrodynamic model calibration and validation [7, 12].

Hydrodynamic models are mathematical models that attempt to replicate fluid motion and typically require solving computationally. These models attempt to simulate water movement by solving the *Navier-Stokes* Equations. Depending on their spatial representation of the floodplain flow, the models can be dimensionally grouped mainly into two categories, 1D and 2D.

Generally, 1D models solve equations derived by satisfying mass and momentum conservation between two cross sections Δx apart, which yields the one-dimensional *Saint-Venant* equations [13].

One dimensional models are mainly used to replicate flow in pipes and surface floodplain flow, in which case flood plain flow is part of the one-dimensional channel flow [9]. One dimensional Saint-Venant equations are a simplification of the two-dimensional shallow water equations which are also known as the two-dimensional Saint-Venant equations. Saint-Venant equations have no analytical solution but can be solved using numerical techniques. The solution of these equations estimates flow and water depth for every cross-section at each time step.

The 2D models represent floodplain flow as a two-dimensional field with the assumption that the third-dimensional water depth is shallow in comparison to the other two dimensions. Most approaches solve the two-dimensional shallow water equations, which represent mass and momentum conservation in a plane, and can be obtained by depth-averaging the Navier-Stokes equations.

The solution of these equations comprises estimates of velocity in two directions over space and time. As with the one-dimensional Saint-Venant equations, the two-dimensional shallow water equations have no analytical solutions. Multiple numerical schemes are therefore developed for algebraic approximation. Depending on numerical discretisation strategies, the model can be classified into finite element, finite difference, and finite volume methods. According to the time discretisation, the model can be divided into implicit (solver cannot proceed to the next time-step until the whole domain is

TABLE I: Flood Simulation Tools.

Empirical Methods	Hydrodynamic Models	Conceptual Simplified Models
Based on observation and historical data.	Mathematical models that attempt to replicate fluid motion based on <i>Shallow Water Equations</i> .	Solve simplified Shallow Water Equations omitting one or two acceleration terms. They do not involve any simulation of the physical processes.
Robust and accurate	No analytical solution and requires numerical schemes.	Approximate predictions of final inundation distributions, with clear benefits in terms of computational cost.
Low computational cost	High computational cost	Useful tools for large scale applications
2D	1D, 2D	2D

solved) and explicit (solving of the current unit independent of solving the rest of the domain for any given time step) models. Finally, in terms of spatial representation, the models can use structured mesh (rectangular grids), unstructured mesh (triangular grids), and most recently, flexible mesh [7].

There is an alternative type of model that can be used in a predictive way but that does not fit the description of a hydrodynamic model. These models should be classified as 2D models due to their dimensional representation of flow. They do not involve any simulation of the physical process of inundation and are based on simplified hydraulic concepts [7].

B. Monitoring Techniques for Floods

Recent work aiming to support disaster management includes an automatic system for near-real time mapping of flood extent and duration using multi-sensor satellite data[14]. The system is based on four processing chains for the automatic derivation of the inundation extent from Sentinel-1(Copernicus Programme satellite) and Terra SAR-X(imaging radar Earth observation satellite) as well as from optical Sentinel-2(Copernicus Programme satellite) and Landsat data. While the systematic acquisition plan of the Sentinel-1/2 and Landsat satellites allows a continuous monitoring of inundated areas at an interval of a few days, the Terra SAR-X processing chain has to be triggered on-demand over the disaster affected areasdata[14].

Additionally, in a recent study [15] an automatic flood-detection method using ALOS-2(satellite) and ancillary data was presented. The authors claim it can be automatically processed and provide easy-to-understand flood information rapidly for users working on-site disaster response. It is based on a Bayesian probabilistic model used for integrating

ancillary data (quasi-real-time flood simulation) and multiple SAR(Synthetic-aperture radar) derived images (amplitude and coherence). Furthermore, incorporating a land-use/land-cover map improved the flood classification result.

Researchers have developed [16] a control strategy for monitoring a dynamically changing flood zone by using a group of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) and an Unmanned Surface Vehicle (USV). The proposed strategy requires to allocate UAVs in the flood area, achieving an optimal coverage efficiency. As the flight duration of UAVs is limited, they need to return to the USV for recharging or for battery swapping.

Disaster robotics has drawn an increasing attention in the recent decade [17] [18]. A challenge identified by FRs, as part of the EU-funded Horizon 2020 PathoCERT project, is the need to identify the extend of the flood and to predict its evolution, using autonomous drones. In this paper, we present a novel approach for solving this challenge, through the use of a single UAV equipped with embedded computing devices to compute the flood maps predictions and to perform on-the-fly path planning, in an autonomous way.

C. Path Planning

Mobile robots are considered autonomous when they are able to create a Path Planning strategy and execute it, without human intervention. For achieving autonomy, a plethora of methods have been proposed from academic and industrial research labs. Specifically, for the problem of autonomous planning and control for ground robots operating in 2D and 2.5D environments [19, 20].

The authors in [21] proposed a new exact mixed-integer linear programming formulation to optimally solve the multi-agent discrete search path planning problem for a stationary object. In the problem model, “open-loop with anticipated feedback” refers to offline planning, while capturing information resulting from predicted agent observations (i.e., projected cell visit action outcome) as opposed to real feedback [21].

Genetic algorithms have also been used in SAR path planning. The authors in [22] introduce a GA-based approach that aims to minimize the mission completion time, which includes the time to find the target (area coverage) and the time to setup a communication path [22].

An approach of various Distributed Particle Swarm Optimization (DPSO)-based path planning algorithms was proposed for UAV swarms conducting a reconnaissance mission. Three algorithms, named the maximum density convergence DPSO algorithm (MDC-DPSO), the fast cross-over DPSO algorithm (FCO-DPSO), and the accurate coverage exploration DPSO algorithm (ACE-DPSO) are proposed correspond to the needs of fast convergence, random cross-over, and accurate search, respectively [23].

In [24], a potential-field method and the A* algorithm are used for trajectory generation. The A* algorithm is used in a 3D

environment, using variations to become hierarchical A* 3D algorithm, and receding horizon A* 3D algorithm [24].

The trajectory computed at each iteration is constrained-to-end in a so-called basis state, in which, the vehicle can safely remain for an indefinite period of time. The principle is applied to the case of a UAV with limited turn rate and minimum speed requirements, for which safety conditions are derived in the form of loiter circles [25].

III. PROBLEM SETUP

In order to respond effectively to the effect of a flood, a suitable flood planning and management strategy is critical. The challenge is within the flood disasters, exposures to calamity of several types and severity (resulting from the flow dynamics of water, rain intensity, wind variation, etc.) create complex environmental issues to deal with. Rapidly occurring flood disasters require a rapid response time as well as fast and coordinated actions of governing authorities and SAR first responders [26].

In practice, flood mitigation strategies [27] developed by authorities can be divided into the following three phases of flood occurrence: a) pre-flood b) in-flood c) post-flood

Given the serious impact of flooding with different characteristics for different regions, it is the ultimate priority that rescue teams and various life-saving response activities in general can rely on an intelligent system for rapid flood monitoring. Evidently, recent advances in UAVs facilitate gathering real-time data from areas of interest, which will enable emergency services to make better decisions at a faster rate.

In our approach, we assume a known Digital Elevation Map (DEM) of the disaster area and the rainfall intensity which are used within LISFLOOD to predict the flood evolution. Our proposed framework uses this information to automatically designate locations for the UAV to visit. In the path-planning phase, the proposed framework provides fine-tuned and collision-free trajectories which incorporate information regarding the agent dynamic and sensing model, the mission objectives and constraints and the mission specifications regarding the locations to be visited. In essence, the path-planning phase computes the optimal low-level control inputs which allow the UAV to autonomously collect data from locations of interest in 3D using its camera system, avoid all obstacles in its way and navigate the surveillance region in a way which is optimal according to the specified mission objectives. To do so, in this work we assume that a controllable UAV agent can operate inside a bounded 3D environment [20]. Additionally, we assume that the UAV departs from its home depot in the beginning of the search mission and reaches the goal region at the end of the mission. Additionally, we assume that:

- a. the UAV agent evolves in time according to a discrete-time dynamical model,

- b. the UAV is equipped with an onboard camera system which exhibits a finite field-of-view (FoV),
- c. the UAV is equipped with an onboard LIDAR sensor which calculates water depth,
- d. the UAV is capable of estimating water velocity.

The proposed search-planning framework considers the low-level mission constraints i.e., the UAV dynamics and the UAV sensing model (i.e., the onboard camera system characteristics) and allows a human operator to specify the initial state (i.e., location) of the agent, the goal region to be reached at the end of the mission (e.g., landing area). The UAV should be able to provide video and water-depth data to the FRs. Finally, the above specifications are transformed using mathematical programming techniques into a Mixed Integer Linear Program (MILP) which is exactly solved using standard off-the-shelf solvers. The output of the proposed framework is an optimal search plan (i.e., a sequence of low-level UAV control inputs over a finite horizon H which meet the mission requirements and optimize the mission objectives).

IV. SYSTEM MODEL

In the current framework we assume that the UAV agent evolves in 3D space according to the following discrete-time linear dynamical model:

$$x_t = \Phi x_{t-1} + \Gamma v_{t-1} \quad (1)$$

where t is the discrete time with sampling time ΔT , and the state vector $x_t = [p_x, p_y, p_z]_t^T \in \mathbb{R}^3$, is the coordinate vector in the Cartesian system of the agent and $v_t = [\nu_x, \nu_y, \nu_z]_t^T \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the velocity vector of the agent in 3D space. The matrices Φ and Γ are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi &= [I_{3 \times 3}] \\ \Gamma &= \Delta T \cdot [I_{3 \times 3}] \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where I is the identity matrix.

The agent is equipped with an onboard camera. Without loss of generality, we assume in this work that the camera Field-of-View (FoV) angles in the horizontal and vertical axis are equal [28] and thus the projected FoV footprint on a planar surface is square with side length r and given by:

$$r(d) = 2d \cdot \arctan\left(\frac{\phi}{2}\right) \quad (3)$$

where d represents the distance in meters between the location of agent and the surface of the ground/water that needs to be monitored and ϕ is the angle opening of the FoV according to the camera specifications. Therefore, the area of the FoV footprint at a distance d is $r(d)$ meters.

In order to monitor the area, the agent needs to take video footage and multiple snapshots such that a predefined area is fully inside the FoV of the camera. The acquired images and video are then processed by an image processing module in

Fig. 2: Representation of the onboard camera Field of View

order to estimate water velocity. Intuitively, the FoV footprint increases as the distance between the agent's location and the surface to be searched increases, allowing the agent to capture a larger area [20]. However, the amount of detail captured in those images inversely decreases with the size of the FoV and as a consequence the probability of estimating the water velocities. On the other hand, as the distance between the agent and the surface shrinks the probability of estimating the water velocity increases. Moreover, the agent's altitude is proportional to the noise measurements of the water depth sensor. Therefore, to ensure that the agent will be at an effective height, margins are set to improve the overall efficiency of the framework.

A. Flood Software Simulation

As indicated above, LISFLOOD-FP's main input data are a DEM (Figure 1) and the rainfall intensity. LISFLOOD is able to simulate and give accurate results for water elevation and water velocities at two dimensions. Illustrations of the simulated results are shown in Figures 3 and 4, respectively.

The cells are automatically selected based on the water momentum. A threshold is set based on the maximum depth of each time interval. The selection progress is described below.

- 1) First the software simulates and returns the estimated water depth and velocities in each cell for the time intervals.
- 2) Within a certain time-span depending on the operation requirements (e.g., 5 minutes) the maximum depth is found and a threshold is set.
- 3) Each cell that is greater than the user selected threshold is considered a target cell.
- 4) The cells that are above the thresholds are set as *areas of interest* and need to be visited.
- 5) The same steps are followed until the simulation data are all exploited.

Fig. 3: Water heights after 1 hour of rainfall

Fig. 4: Water Velocities in each cell of the map

However, the previous steps describe a rather dynamic environment. In essence, the cells cannot be fully predicted a-priori. In recent years Model Predictive Control (MPC) is commonly used to create online path generation and it is incorporated in this application to handle the dynamic environment [29]. While the first batch of cells is set, a MPC algorithm is deployed to generate a trajectory for the drone. While the drone is navigating above cells it collects data, in parallel the next path is being calculated. With the proposed technique, the drone is able to dynamically and autonomously navigate during flood events.

B. Mathematical Problem Formulation

Hereafter, we detail how we have encoded the 3D search task into mathematical programming constraints. In essence, we would like to make sure that the UAV agent will pass through the areas of interest during the mission as indicated by selected characteristics of cells in LISFLOOD scenarios.

In order to simplify the notation, and without loss of generality, we describe the 3D search task for one batch of cells (considering 1-minute time-span). The constraints in Eqs. 4 - 7 define the agent's 3D trajectory space, where τ is the prediction step and t is the LISFLOOD output step time at the k -th target cell. Let $b^{max} = [b_x^{max}, b_y^{max}, b_z^{max}]^T$ and $b^{min} = [b_x^{min}, b_y^{min}, b_z^{min}]^T$ serve as binary indicators of the UAV agent position in 3D space. Finally N , $\tau \in 1, \dots, N$ is the prediction horizon for which the MPC problem is solved.

$$Ax_{\tau|t} < HG_{k|t}^T + M(1 - b_{k,\tau}^{max}) \quad \forall \tau, t, k \quad (4)$$

$$Ax_{\tau|t} > LG_{k|t}^T + M(1 - b_{k,\tau}^{min}) \quad \forall \tau, t, k \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{\tau=1}^N (b_{k,\tau}^{max} + b_{k,\tau}^{min}) - 5 > -M(1 - z_{k,\tau}) \quad \forall k \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{\tau=1}^N z_{k,\tau} > 0 \quad (7)$$

Assuming that $H \cdot G^T$ and $L \cdot G^T$ are the vectors that represent the boundaries of the area that needs to be explored Equations 4 - 5 are responsible to drive the solution in those boundaries.

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} I_{3 \times 3} \\ 0_{3 \times 3} \end{bmatrix}, H = \begin{bmatrix} I_{3 \times 3} & 0_{3 \times 3} \\ 0_{3 \times 3} & 0_{3 \times 3} \end{bmatrix}, L = \begin{bmatrix} 0_{3 \times 3} & 0_{3 \times 3} \\ 0_{3 \times 3} & I_{3 \times 3} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

$$G = [p_x^{max}, p_y^{max}, p_z^{max}, p_x^{min}, p_y^{min}, p_z^{min}]_{k,t} \quad (9)$$

Additionally, the binary variable b is activated when the constraints are in the respective boundaries. This is achieved with the Big- M method that enables the constraints to always be valid in order for the optimization problem to have a feasible solution. The same constraints are applied in all three dimensions. In Equation 6 the binary variable z is activated when the all the boundary constraints are valid, hence when the agent is in-between the 6 boundaries. To assure that at least one cell is visited, Equation 7 is employed and forces the summation of binary variables to be greater than zero.

In order for the agent to fulfil its mission, an objective function is constructed to handle the aforementioned objectives. The required objective function is a combination of three weighted terms, namely: the Input Fluctuation Penalty (IFP), the Time Penalty (TP) and the Sensor Penalty (SP):

$$\text{Input Fluctuation Penalty: } f_T = \sum_{\tau=1}^N |v_{\tau-1} - v_{\tau}| \quad (10)$$

$$\text{Time Penalty: } g_T = \sum_{\tau=1}^N z_{\tau} \quad (11)$$

$$\text{Sensor Penalty: } s_T = \sum_{\tau=1}^N p_z^{\tau} \cdot z_{\tau} \cdot f(\tau), \quad (12)$$

where T is the planning horizon (i.e., the total amount of time allocated for the mission). As we can observe from Eqn. 11 it

forces the agent to reach the cells position as soon as possible i.e., at the earliest time-step. For this reason, the minimization of TP also minimizes the search operation execution time. Additionally, in Eqn.11, by driving the agent to visit as fast as possible the cells, enables the framework to take measurements in shorter times, hence enhances the ability of the UAV to reschedule efficient trajectories. On the other hand, the Input Fluctuation Penalty in Eqn.10 is used in order to minimize the fluctuations between consecutive control inputs thus leading to smoother trajectories (i.e., smooth trajectories with less abrupt changes). The SP term models the water depth sensor and assures the UAV will take measurements with the accepted error. The binary indicator is multiplied with the agents altitude then multiplied with the linear equation $f(\tau) = N - \tau + 1$. Furthermore, in this work we consider that the minimization of the UAV's control input variation is directly related to the reduction of the UAV's energy consumption. We assume that by reducing the variation between consecutive controls, abrupt changes in the control input are eliminated, leading to more energy efficient operation [20]. Overall, the objective function of the search mission is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{minimize } J &= w_1 f_T + w_2 g_T + w_3 s_T & (13) \\ |v_t| &< v_{max} \\ p_z &\in [0, P_z] \\ b, z &\in \{0, 1\} \\ \text{Eqns. (1) - (12)} \end{aligned}$$

where the weights w_1, w_2 and w_3 are tuned according to the mission requirements and in essence determine the balance given between the mission execution time and the mission energy efficiency.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS:

To evaluate the proposed approach we have run extensive scenarios using both LISFLOOD simulations and the proposed MPC controller implemented in Matlab. Running the simulations focuses on evaluating the effectiveness of the proposed solutions on approaching the "Ground Truth" trajectory, where the "Ground Truth" is considered the path the UAV should have followed based on the rainfall intensity. The time horizon for each MPC is set at $N = 100$ and the overall simulation time is set to 1 minute which translates to 60-time steps. After the 60-time steps are executed, the cells values are once more updated using LISFLOOD before re-optimizing the UAV trajectory using the proposed MPC approach. The parameters of the multi-objective function are set to $w_1 = 10.0$, $w_2 = 4$, $w_3 = 400$.

For the second stage of the experiment we assume the rainfall intensity (as set in LISFLOOD in each cell) is not known to the user and the drone will autonomously converge to the correct rainfall after collecting data from the ground truth water depth. Hence in the latter scenario we assume that at each visited cell measurements are made for the UAV to autonomously estimate which is the most probable rainfall rate and thus correct its

path planning choices. For this stage of the experiment four methods were used. Each method used the measurement taken and compare either the water depth or the water momentum with all the pre-simulated flood scenarios. In essence, the scenario that has the less statistical difference is selected as the best fit and the UAV recalculates the cells based on current rainfall rate believes. The same procedure is then repeated at each execution step of the MPC. The water depth sensor measurements are modelled as in Eqn.14.

$$\begin{aligned} m_{i,j} &= wd_{i,j} + n \quad \forall j, i \\ i &\in \{1, l_x\} \\ j &\in \{1, l_y\} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where wd is the real water depth, m is the drone measurement, l_x and l_y are the grid lengths in the Euclidean space. The measurement error n is random and unbiased and has standard deviation $\sigma_n = 0.5$.

A. Modelling Data

For the experimental evaluation the DEM of the Nicosia city center in Cyprus was used. Firstly, 40 different rainfall rates were selected to test the framework's performance. For each of the rates, LISFLOOD-FP calculated the water depth that would occurred in Nicosia in the range of 1 hour. Additionally, the margins of the area are set to 79×83 cells and each cell side is set at $25m$. We assume that there are no reflections of the water flow at the edge of the simulation bounty box. Initial conditions of the simulation assumes that the surface is dry ($wd = 0$) at the beginning of the simulation. All the simulations are set to run for a simulation time of 1 hour with one second interval.

B. Methods

The framework's objective is to enable the agent to distinguish which rainfall rate is happening in real time. Three statistical methods are evaluated and the fittest was implemented in order to enhance the ability of the UAV agent to generate efficient trajectories. The first approach followed the t-test based methodology on the Student's t-distribution, which is widely used. It is the theoretical basis for hypothesis testing and interval estimation of the population mean. The t-test theory is based on the t distribution theory to compare whether the difference is significant or not. In this work, t-test is used to test if the measurement is statistically different from each of the database water depths/momentum data. When the null hypothesis is not rejected, that means the measurement is not statistically different from the specific water depth, therefore there is a possibility that the ground truth matches the scenario. The higher the p-value, the higher the possibility of a match [30].

The second method used is the z-test. The test checks the possibility that two samples have distributions with the same means [31]. It is worth stating that hypothesis tests between two means are part of parametric statistics and are only recommended when the sample sizes are at least 30 or the data

distribution is approximately normally distributed. Given two independent samples, taken from two populations, each sample has its own mean a hypothesis test to compare these two means is incorporated by z-test. The decision if the two means are significantly different is based on the p-value obtained using the result of z-test. If the p-value is smaller than the significance level obtained, the null hypothesis is rejected, otherwise it is accepted.

Finally the Wilcoxon signed-rank test is a non-parametric statistical hypothesis test used either to test the location of a set of samples or to compare the locations of two populations using a set of matched samples.

C. Performance Results and Analysis

Table II shows the mean accuracy based on experimental results. In particular, the same test were run 10 times and a mean accuracy was calculated to explore which method is better suited. Analysing the data and focusing in moving time windows it is observable that at different time windows the accuracy differs significantly for each method. Additionally, the maximum accuracy was achieved by z-test and with significant difference from the second t-test. Consequently an important factor that affects the accuracy of the methods is the number of the measurements combined with the time taken. Finally, taking into considerations that the parameters are for all the experiments the same, it is shown that the z-test performed better overall.

It is worth mentioning that the accuracy decreased while measuring the water momentum. The decrease implies that the small values of velocities are approaching zero, making it difficult for the methods to distinguish the fittest rainfall scenario.

For the path-planning experiments, two frameworks were used. The z-test framework and the simpler Euclidean distance framework that compares the difference between measurements and simulated data. Based on the minimum distance, the fittest scenario is chosen as acting rainfall rate. The path planning mainly focuses on the problem of data collection with multiple mission areas, which requires UAVs to determine the optimal trajectory for data collection. Figures 6 and 7 summarizes the simulation results for three trajectories of a UAV. After a UAV departs from the initial position, the UAV constantly updates its position according to the data collection and the determination of the rainfall rate.

The illustrated paths denote the different trajectories of the UAVs based on the z-test framework, Euclidean framework and the “optimal path”. The optimal path is based on waypoints derived from the scenario serving as the ground truth. Comparing the three trajectories, the distance covered by the UAV agent with the z-test, Euclidean frameworks are 6.6098km and 5.9050km, respectively while the Ground truth distance was in total 6.0888km. Although the distance covered doesn’t necessarily shows that one framework is superior than the other, when comparing the trajectories it is visible that

z-test approximates better the Ground Truth trajectory. The RMSE between the z-test path, Euclidean path and the Ground Truth are presented in Figure 5. In the process of monitoring and collecting data the UAV must also maximize the amount of visited mission cells in a predefined short time window. Mission cells are cells that contain imperative data for the flood event. Without the implementation of the convergence method the UAV is wasting energy on collecting redundant data and since the UAV has energy limitation the efficiency of the UAV agent is proportionally decreasing.

Fig. 5: RMSE of Euclidean Distance, z-test and Ground Truth

Fig. 6: Trajectory z-test of UAV in comparison with Ground Truth

Fig. 7: Trajectory euclidean of UAV in comparison with Ground Truth

	1800-1900	1900-2000	Time[s]			Overall	Max	Min
			2000-2100	2100-2200	2200-2300			
z-test	69%	83%	77%	46%	63%	67%	78%	62%
t-test	87%	70%	68%	45%	48%	63%	70%	60%
Wilcoxon	83%	75%	57%	55%	40%	61%	68%	54%

TABLE II: Result tables.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This work proposed a novel framework for UAV path planning, which considers trajectories through waypoints emerging from a hydrological simulation model, with a focus of rapid data collection during flooding emergency management.

In particular, the proposed framework plans the motion of a UAV dynamically by adjusting the waypoints based on the influence of a flood-simulator (LISFLOOD), whose data are fused with the UAV-collected data. For the path planning framework, an optimization problem was formulated in terms of cost minimization under constraints in an MPC framework. Regarding the rainfall convergences, four methods were derived and used. Simulation results demonstrated promising performance, in terms of efficient data collection and accuracy.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreements No 883484 (PathoCERT) and 739551 (KIOS CoE TEAMING) and from the Republic of Cyprus through the Deputy Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digital Policy.

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